

IN THE SOCIAL MESH: THEORETICAL INSIGHTS INTO NETWORKED WELL-BEING

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Abstract

Social networks refer to the intricate web of social relationships and connections that individuals have with others. These relationships can take various forms, structures, processes and methods including friendships, family ties, professional connections, acquaintances and membership in social groups or communities. To understand various perspectives of social networks the Network theory offers a powerful and expressive framework for analysing and synthesizing collectives whose members exert social influence on one another. When such a collective makes a social choice, all social relationships that potentially impact the decision must be considered. Historically, the development of social relationships to social networking came under the theoretical concern with the study of human behaviour and has fallen under the scope of the social sciences. This paper will theoretically study different forms of social interactions and networking procedures that maintain social well-being in everyday life, which encompass a wide range of disciplines including sociology, social psychology, economics, public health, and epidemiology.

Key Words: Social Network and well-being, Network Analysis Theory, Social Bonding

Introduction

Social networks, comprising the intricate tapestry of relationships forged through various interactions, have long been recognized as fundamental to human existence. From familial ties to friendships, professional networks to online communities, these connections serve as conduits for support, information exchange, and emotional nourishment. At the heart of this exploration lies the fundamental question: How do these networks influence our well-being? Delving into this inquiry unravels a multifaceted landscape where the dynamics of social interconnectedness intersect with psychological, emotional, and even physical dimensions of wellness. Research across disciplines has shed light on the intricate mechanisms through which social networks contribute to well-being. Whether through the provision of social support during challenging times, the amplification of positive emotions through shared experiences, or the cultivation of a sense of belonging and identity, the impact of social networks reverberates deeply within individuals and communities alike. Yet, this relationship is not without complexities. As we navigate the digital age, where virtual connections often supplement or even replace face-to-face interactions, new questions arise about the nature and quality of these relationships and their implications for well-being. Moreover, disparities in access to social networks highlight broader issues of social inequality and their ramifications for health and happiness.

Social network develops within the social environment, that is shaped by individuals' familial, friendship, relational, and acquaintanceship networks. The network view primarily emphasizes the meso-level of social relationships among individuals. The social environment can be seen as a framework of social connections that either enables or constrains the range of actions available to individuals. Additionally, it has an impact on how individuals perceive themselves and their capacity to engage in actions. The term "social well-being" is used to describe how satisfied people are with their social lives and relationships within their communities. It includes a person's ability to interact with others, their relationships, and their

sense of place in and responsibility to society as a whole. As important as one's physical, mental, and emotional health are, one's quality of life is profoundly impacted by their social health as well.

Typically, this functional aspect of social relationships comprises forms in terms of emotional, instrumental, and informational support. Emotional support refers to the availability of social contacts for conversations about one's own emotions, which can contribute to the discussion of everyday fears and concerns or provide confirmation of sympathy and affection (Lin et al., 1999). Instrumental support consists of those forms of aid that are distinguished by their instrumental nature. Informational support encompasses all services that provide knowledge for solving particular problems or access to particular resources, such as within communities.

The majority of social support originates from intimate, relatively robust social relationships. In contrast, the concept of social capital distinguishes between strong and weak relationships. Weak social ties are more likely to yield fresh knowledge and resources. This relates the concept to the concept of social networks in an intimate manner. It has been referred to as the strength of weak connections (Granovetter, 1973; Putnam, 1995). According to Granovetter's thesis, it is not the frequent, close, and intense relationships (also known as bonding social capital) that provide pertinent resources, such as labour market access. Rather, these resources can be obtained through contacts with a diminished frequency and intensity. These contacts, known as bridging social capital, are distinguished by the fact that they are established across various social groups and that they increase the likelihood of gaining access to particular resources (Lin et al., 1999). In contrast, more intimate relationships are more likely to provide material and emotional support (Dahl & Malmberg-Heimonen, 2010). Both social capital and social cohesion carry with them the potential for negative processes within social organizations. These include social exclusion, stigmatization, discrimination, and other negative effects of social relationships, including ongoing conflicts (Kawachi & Berman, 2014). Additionally, groups with high social cohesion have minimal contact with other groups. Positive attitudes toward others can be bolstered and prejudice and negative attitudes can be diminished through contact between diverse groups. This has been studied in the context of various ethnic groups (Laurence & Bentley, 2016; Hewstone, 2015) and discussed through the lens of two distinct theories: conflict theory (Putnam, 2007) and intergroup contact theory (Brown & Hewstone, 2005).

Various scientific fields, including physics, biology, psychology, and sociology, have accepted network theories, but these respective approaches are not always transferable to other fields and complicate a shared theoretical foundation. White (1995); Gibson (2005); Fuhse (2008) are the only authors who have attempted to populate relational analysis with cultural and symbolic aspects based on theoretical considerations to explain actions and interactions. Consequently, social networks are initially more than an individual's social contacts. Social networks differ from social integration in that they permit statements to be made about the structure of social contacts, i.e., they illustrate the interconnectedness of the alteri, as revealed by individual social contacts. Thus, this concept of network exceeds the comprehension of networks reflected in the aforementioned indices (such as the Social Network Index). In terms of social capital, the concept of social network is limited in that it not only describes what resources or norms and values are available in certain groups but also concentrates on how these are created and reproduced, as well as what patterns of social networks enable or impede the availability of particular resources. Such a network concept challenges the structural conditionality of social support and can therefore complement research on social support, as concentrating on individual forms and patterns of support neglects the social structure underlying perceived or actual support. Social cohesion can be used to characterize the connectivity of social networks.

I. Components of Social Networks and Well-Being

The primary focus of this study is to relate components of social networks and how they influence social well-being, which encompasses the analysis of both individual interactions or dyads, as well as the interconnectedness of these relationships and the structural organization of links within a network (Marin & Wellman, 2011; Borgatti & Halgin, 2011). The concept of interactive units, such as individuals, couples, families, and other entities, including institutions or organizations, can be comprehended as networks of actors. The acquisition and perpetuation of cultural norms and values by individuals involved in acting are influenced by socialization processes and daily encounters with their fellow actors, which may also lead to modifications in these norms and values. According to Granovetter (1985), actors in the realm of network theory are seen to be "embedded" within a relational network of social connections, which can either expand or limit their potential for engaging in various actions (Emirbayer & Mische, 1998). The influence of individuals inside a network is contingent upon their position or "embedding" within the network, as well as the makeup and structure of the network itself.

The components of the social network are "friendship" (Delitsch, 1900), "social circles" (Simmel, 1950), "social integration" (Moreno, 1934), "social structure" (Radcliffe-Brown, 1940), "role concept" (Nadel, 1957), and "figurations" (Elias, 1978) have been discussed in the fields of sociology, social anthropology, and psychology which associated with structural analysis are relatively recent developments (Freeman, 2004). This segment presents and examines key ideas such as social support, social capital, social cohesiveness, and social networks, building upon the aforementioned fundamental distinction.

a) Social Support, Assistance and Wellbeing:

Social support is the primary qualitative dimension at the micro-level of social relationships. Social support is impossible without social contacts and integration into social networks by which an individual withdraws his or her well-being. If the quantity of social relationships is measured by the number and frequency of social contacts, then the character of these relationships is measured by social support. (Turner & Marino, 1994) Support research distinguishes between objective and subjective aspects of support. It has been demonstrated that an individual's perception of available support can have a positive effect, for example on mental health and wellbeing without necessarily requiring the actual receipt of support. Without receiving actual support, the perception of social support can mitigate the negative effects of acute stress (Cobb, 1976; House et al., 1988; Turner & Marino, 1994; Uchino, 2009). In addition, little correlation has been discovered between received support and subjectively perceived support, indicating that each can be viewed as a relatively independent construct (Barrera, 1986; Lakey & Cohen, 2000).

b) Social reciprocity:

It is a significant idea within the realm of social assistance, as highlighted by Siegrist and colleagues. Social reciprocity is a crucial principle of social support (Siegrist & Winkler, 2003).

Wahrendorf et al., 2016). People anticipate a recompense for their generosity (principle of reciprocity). This expectation of reciprocity facilitates the formation of social interactions. A service rendered in exchange need not be identical to the service received, but it should be perceived as adequate and comparable.

The reciprocity norm can vary based on the nature of the relationships involved. Within the family, one is more inclined to provide a service without expecting temporally indirect compensation from close friends or relatives. Generalized reciprocity implies that services are provided without exception those that have not been provided individually are always

returned in kind. Rather, general reciprocity can be anticipated at a much later time, such as in parent-child relationships.

c) Social capital and social network:

Multiple disciplines (sociology, economics, social psychology, and politics) investigate social capital as a subject of study. (Berkman & Krishna, 2014; Kawachi & Berkman, 2014) Social capital is understood to be a resource of social networks that only develop through social interaction with others. In sociology, two research traditions can be distinguished: a French research tradition exemplified by Bourdieu and an American research tradition that includes James's work. Coleman and Putnam Robert. Both perspectives on social capital are distinct. Following Bourdieu's capital theory, in addition to economic capital, cultural capital and social capital are available. Social capital means that access to resources is facilitated by social relationships (Bourdieu, 2000). In turn, social capital can influence other forms of capital. One could conceive of a "competition between investments in social capital and other capital" (Lüdicke & Diewald, 2007, p. 15, authors' translation). Social capital is viewed as a characteristic of individuals who can engage in commerce with or through it. Coleman (1990) and Putnam (1990) view social capital as a characteristic of social networks; consequently, the focus is on the interpersonal level. "Unlike other forms of capital, social capital inheres in the structure of relationships between and among actors" (Coleman, 1990, p. 98). This Northern American custom gained knowledge of social capital through the study of social networks. The question of how and under what conditions social capital is formed in social networks is in the foreground (Lin, 2000).

When examining social capital at the individual level, there is an overlap between the concepts of social support and social networks. At the meso- or macro-level, social capital can be characterized as both a property of social organizations and a feature of habitats or communities. Based on the recording of individual assessments, such as reciprocity and trust in the respective living environment (e.g., neighbourhood, district), social and voluntary commitment, and general attitudes toward groups or living spaces, aggregate indices that reflect the extent of social capital are formulated and employed. correspondingly as attributes of groups or defined spaces. The fundamental assumption is that only through experienced reciprocity and trust, as well as based on shared values and norms, does regular interaction emerge, which in turn facilitates access to resources within groups and the development of social capital (Putnam, 1995; Putnam et al., 2001). Therefore, the greater the level of trust in one's living environment, the more likely it is that stable social relationship structures will emerge. Several investigations have confirmed the existence of such associations (Airaksinen et al., 2015; Pickett & Pearl, 2001).

d) Social Integration and Unity:

Social cohesion is another frequently used term in the field of social relations. Social cohesion refers to the subjective evaluations of the connections between group members. There is a certain degree of social cohesion within each group. (Bollen & Hoyle, 1990) distinguish between structural cohesion and perceived cohesion, a sensation of togetherness among the individual members. By accentuating the feeling of belonging, which includes the concept of perceived social cohesion closely parallels the concept of social capital in terms of shared values and norms. A high level of structural social cohesion indicates that the members of a group are closely interconnected. Therefore, the strongest cohesion within a group is achieved when every member of a network is directly connected to every other member, whereas the lowest cohesion is achieved when many members of a network are only loosely and indirectly connected. The subjective and structural cohesion are not required to coincide. Social cohesion is characterized as a feature.

Social cohesion is frequently measured through subjective evaluations. Individual assessments and perceptions of the respective groups, as well as the actual activities of individuals within groups, are emphasized. Strong cohesion within social organizations is frequently accompanied by an increase in internal social control, while these groups remain relatively close to the outside world (Kawachi & Berkman, 2014). Examples of such cohesive groups can be found among immigrants who, due to language and other social barriers, are apt to form strong ties among themselves but remain relatively closed to the outside world. The same holds for densely interconnected neighbourhoods and villages.

II Theoretical Understanding of Social Networks

Social networks involve the application of a social science concept rooted in action theory. This theory posits that humans are not isolated entities, but rather exist within a network of interpersonal relationships. This perspective is supported by scholars such as Burt (1982), Emirbayer (1997), and Granovetter (1985). The interactions among actors have a crucial role in shaping the actions and conduct of individuals inside a network (Wellman, 1988). The theoretical framework proposed by Emirbayer and Goodwin (1994) posits that social processes and acts cannot be fully accounted for by individual-level factors, such as sociodemographic variables (e.g., age, gender, ethnicity, and education level).

Social Systems and Networks:

Sociological network analysis is more concerned with the relationships between individuals and the characteristics of these relationships than with the characteristics of the individuals themselves. Individual actions are embedded in a network of interpersonal relationships, according to Burt (1982). Network analysis examines the entirety of a network of relationships. The relationship between the ego and the alters is also influenced by the relationships between the alteri themselves (alter-alter-ties), which are in turn influenced by the relationships between the ego and the alter's indirect relationship with the ego. Social interaction and social processes can be explained not only by an individual's characteristics but also by their integration into a social environment (Light & Moody, 2020). To depict these social relationships, graphical network models are devised. From the perspective of network research, the individual's micro perspective is soon abandoned. The Individual and group interdependencies illustrated at the meso-level are of interest.

Not only can the position of an individual within a social network be identified, but by disclosing the structures of a network, the opportunities for contact, influence, and control within networks can be analyzed. These structures can be characterized by network theory, Holzer (2009) uses concepts such as nodes, density, centrality, and position to characterize social phenomena. The numerous forms and types of possible interactions between individuals and groups contribute to the complexity of social networks. For instance, egocentric networks focus on the relationships between a given ego and its alteri, whereas socio-centric or complete networks emphasize the relationships between egos.

All relationships between network members within a given and constrained social network (such as a community). In addition, social networks can be differentiated based on their respective nature, which can be formal in the case of organizations and associations or informal in the case of personal, kinship, or friendship networks and contacts. In addition, networks can be differentiated according to their frequency, intensity, size, and reach, which is referred to as their extension. Early research on social networks primarily emphasized these quantitative aspects of social relationships. The concepts of social networks and social integration overlap in this context. Laireiter (1993) defines social integration as the incorporation of individuals into social groups, associations, or voluntary organizations; the number of social contacts with family, relatives, and friends; and the accessibility and

availability of social and interpersonal resources. Likewise, social integration refers to norms and values as orientations for individual actions, which are produced and maintained through social interaction. Multiple indicators were developed to quantify the level of social integration within social networks.

Regarding network theory, John Scott contends, "Theoretical work in social network analysis has been underdeveloped for decades." While the methods themselves do not require or imply a specific sociological theory, they do require contextualisation within broader debates" (Scott, 2011, p. 24). Since the beginning of the twentieth century, there has been intense theoretical debate on the concept of social relations and their structures, even though the theorization of networks has been neglected for a long time. Generally speaking, it is assumed that individuals are embedded in relationships and cannot be viewed apart from their social environment. Individual dyads, or relationships between two actors, are linked to networks of larger entities. The meso-level is where networks reside. Thus, they serve as a bridge between the micro-level, or individual action (agency), and the macro-level, or institutions (Weyer, 2012, p. 241). Consequently, networks are comprised of actors who develop relationships with one another, and these relationships produce broader social structures. The theoretical focus is not on so-called classical characteristics of individuals or institutions, such as gender, ethnicity, or age, but on relationships and their structures. Relationships, the embeddedness of individuals within a network, and the interaction between social structure and individual characteristics are the basis for research questions.

Theories of networks may consist of "grand theories" and "middle-range theories." Grand theories incorporate generalizations and extensive evidence. (Mills, 1968) These are relatively distinct from actual concerns of daily existence. Middle-range theories are situated between global and research-focused working theories of social networks. They are also limited to a particular discipline of study (Merton, 1968). Accordingly, there are three ideal-typical modes of network research (Emirbayer & Goodwin, 1994). The first is structuralist determinism, which relies solely on relational characteristics to explain the actions of actors while ignoring cultural discourses. The actions are predetermined by the network structure and the individualization within these structures. Structuralist instrumentalism emphasizes the individual's action options, which stem from his or her position in the network. Homo economicus uses these options instrumentally, in the sense of structural individualism, for their benefit. Social actors have a greater influence on theoretical interests than structural determinism.

In structure-based Constructivism, social structures, culture, and action are regarded as distinct but interconnected aspects. Culture is influenced by the networks and individuals that comprise it. They stand on equitable footing side by side. Relationships are understood as a component constructed by the actors themselves, which makes the perception of the participating actors even more significant (Emirbayer & Sahlin, 2004). Although these three ideal types are distinct, they all presume that individuals' actions and identities are influenced by their relationships and context. In addition, the theories demonstrate that actors build networks that can be transmitted to institutions and consolidated. The focus of the analysis may vary, but they all begin with the human as a social actor connected to others through networks. Therefore, networks are "... a set of relevant nodes connected by one or more relations" (Marin & Wellman, 2011, p. 11). To illustrate the above-described relational reasoning, examples of "grand theories" and "middle-range theories" will be provided in the following section. The focus, however, is on "middle-range theories," as these are of greater significance in empirical research.

Grand Theory in Network Analysis

Georg Simmel's works likely contain one of the earliest theoretical discussions of networks (Simmel, 1950 [1908]). While Simmel refers to social circles, he refers to the relational integration of social networks. Primary social circles are social formations (such as families and tribes) into which an individual is born. These circles are distinguished by their intense emotional closeness, brief path distances, and high level of trust. On the other hand, rational circles (such as business or partnership relationships) are predicated on logic on shared interests and "homophily." Actors engage in relationships, which in turn influence the actions of the individuals and expand or restrict their options. Each person's uniqueness is shaped by his or her affiliation with various circles. (Hollstein, 2001) Simmel has already identified the first basic structural characteristics that can be utilized in network analysis.

Sigfried Nadel, an Austrian ethnologist, is another significant relational thinker. He distinguishes between function, connection, and social structure. Roles are regarded as network outcomes. They are generated by the interaction of actors. Actors do not exclusively possess the characteristics of their roles. Due to the relationship between role templates and cultural norms and laws, they are relatively stable (e.g., friendships). The description and definition of a role's values create expectations among a network's actors. In the social analysis of sociologist Norbert Elias (2014 [1970]), networks play a crucial function. He refers to figurations, which means that individuals are interdependent and influence social interaction, as well as the actors themselves. According to him, individuals are, due to their fundamental dispositions and preferences,

Theories of Middle-Range Networks

In addition to grand theories, there are middle-range theories that emphasize relationships and social networks. In some instances, these explanations can be subsumed under comprehensive theories, which are more empirically grounded. Middle-range theories are useful not only for developing hypotheses but also for interpreting and describing research findings.

a) Solid or Weak Ties

Granovetter (1973) was the originator of a crucial relational concept. In his methodology, the sociologist distinguishes between strong and feeble relationships (ties) based on their intensity. "(probably linear) combination of the amount of time, the emotional intensity, the intimacy (mutual confiding), and the reciprocal services [...]" (Granovetter, 1973, p. 1361) distinguishes between strong and weak relationships. Strong relationships are marked by, for example: For instance, reciprocity, intense contact, high intimacy and emotion, and trust. This includes members of the family and even close acquaintances. Conversely, weak connections are loose relationships with characteristics such as low contact frequency and low intimacy.

b) Homophily (Selection/Influence)

An important concept in network research is homophily. Lazarsfeld and Merton (1954), who combined observations of classical network studies with ethnographic research on marriage formation, coined the term as we know it today. This translates to "birds of a feather flock together." The authors here distinguish between "status homophily" and "value homophily." The former refers to attributes such as race, gender, religion, and level of education. "Value homophily" also refers to individuals who share similar attitudes or methods of thinking, regardless of their status. This implies that, in terms of networks, people form relationships with those who are similar to them (Lazarsfeld and Weick, 2003). McPherson et al. (2001) note that ethnicity, age, religious affiliation, education, gender, and occupation are significant

factors within networks: "Homophily in race and ethnicity creates the strongest divides in our environments, with age, religion, education, occupation, and gender following in roughly that order" (p. 415).

Additionally, there is the concept of "popularity." According to this middle-range theory, some actors "own" more relationships than others and are, as a result, more popular than other actors in the network. A further theory presupposes that actors who already "own" numerous relationships may receive even more relationship requests as a result. Popular individuals are those with whom many actors wish to establish a rapport. Initial research indicates that students who are intellectual, extroverted, and competent are more well-known or popular than others (Bonney, 1946; Young & Cooper, 1944).

c) The principle of reciprocity

Reciprocity is an essential principle in network research. Reciprocity presupposes that individuals anticipate a gift or action to be returned or balanced. The principle of gift and gift in return (Mauss, 1954) and the networks that result from this process enter into play at this point. Numerous forms of social interaction and networks are enabled by the varying expectations of gifts and gifts in return. In Simmel's (1950 [1908]) view,

It is a fundamental principle of society in general. Transactions between actors are not always governed by an official, monetary price or formal (e.g., legal) norms. A service or gift in return need not be identical or paid in the same form as the service or gift received, but it should be perceived as adequate and comparable. Culture, historical context, and the nature of the actors involved (e.g., friend and acquaintance) influence reciprocity norms.

Conclusion

Sociological understanding of social networks and their relationship with wellbeing is a complex and multifaceted topic that has been the subject of extensive research. Social networks refer to the web of social relationships, which is developed by each individual according to their capacity to develop relationships, bonding and attachments with others at micro, meso and macro levels.

Social networks develop Positive and meaningful relationships with family, friends, coworkers, and the community at large are fundamental to social well-being. Having friends and family nearby can be a great source of comfort and belonging. Having a solid group of friends and family to lean on is crucial to your emotional and mental health. Social networks encourage participation in civic, social, and cultural activities that can improve people's quality of life in many ways. Doing something for the greater good of others, like volunteering or joining a group or organization, can fall under this category. Feeling respected and accepted by one's community is central to one's sense of social inclusion and, by extension, to one's sense of social well-being. However, being shut out of society can have negative repercussions on health. The level of social capital in a community is a key factor in that community's social well-being. Cooperation and mutual aid within a community are made possible by its members' social capital, which consists of their networks, relationships, and shared values and standards. When people in a society have a lot of social capital, it helps build trust, cooperation, and stability. The ability to identify with and participate in one's community is crucial to one's emotional and mental health. It helps one feel like they belong and have something to live for. Interpersonal and communication competence is crucial for establishing and maintaining positive relationships, handling problems constructively, and increasing mutual understanding and compassion. Social and cultural norms and values have an impact on people's quality of life. Community members' actions, relationships, and feelings of acceptance can all be shaped by these conventions. Social health is one factor that contributes to an individual's ability to persevere in the face of adversity. People who have

solid networks of friends and family behind them are better able to weather the storms of life. To improve people's social lives, communities should be designed to encourage supportive relationships among residents. It also necessitates working to eliminate social barriers and injustices. By advocating for policies and programs that fortify social bonds and advance social fairness, governments, communities, and individuals can all contribute to improving social well-being.

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